

Tool 9

Map your stakeholders

Welcome to the Citizen Science Starter Kit.

This template is part of Module 4 “Getting started with citizen science” (phase 1 – Prepare), which helps you to map and analyse your stakeholders.

Please download this template to your own folder and fill it in on your local computer. If you have any further questions about this template, please contact citizenscience@vub.be.

Step 1. Identify potential stakeholders

Think of all the people and organizations that might be affected by your project. Who has influence or power over it? Who might have an interest in its conclusions?

To get you started, Göbler et al.² identified the following six main stakeholder groups in citizen science:

- (1) Civil society organizations, informal groups and community members
- (2) Academic and research organizations
- (3) Government agencies and departments
- (4) Participants
- (5) Formal learning institutions such as schools
- (6) Businesses or industry

Consider also this additional table of potential stakeholders to broaden your scope. But don't stop here – each project has its own specific context. Try to identify and name your stakeholders as concretely as possible. While some of them might be *organizations*, it is also useful to identify the relevant individuals within that organization.

Potential stakeholders of your research (project)		
Research manager	Community-based organizations	Software providers
Neighbourhood organizations	Funders	Interest groups or standardization bodies involved in your research topic
Your co-workers	Faith-based organisations	The press
Local inhabitants	Educational organizations	Street workers
Students	Industry (e.g. infrastructure)	Community health workers
Social service organisations	Sensor companies	Key advisors or experts in the theme
Museums	Libraries	FabLabs
Local cities or towns	Intergovernmental organisations	Policy makers at European level

Step 2: Prioritize your stakeholders

Once you have identified your relevant stakeholders, it is time to prioritize them. This allows you to know which ones to focus on, without forgetting about the less important ones. A power/interest duality can help you to classify your stakeholders according to their power over your research and their interest in it.

Step 3: Understand your key stakeholders

To understand your key stakeholders and engage with them in meaningful ways, these are questions which could be answered (with or without their direct input).

- What (social, political, financial, ...) interest do they have in the outcome of your research?
- What motivates them most of all?

- What information do they want from you, and what is the best way of communicating with them?
- What is their current opinion of your research?
- Who influences their opinions generally, and who influences their opinion of you? Do some of these influencers therefore become important stakeholders in their own right?
- If they aren't likely to be positive, what will motivate them to support your project?
- Who else might be influenced by their opinions? Do these people become stakeholders in their own right?

Step 4: Define the level of engagement

Determine for each prioritized stakeholder if they will be involved according to a low or high level of engagement, and which potential activities they can do. The table of Shirk et al. might be helpful to categorize your stakeholders.

Stakeholder 1:	
Stakeholder 2:	
Stakeholder 3:	
....	

Table 2. Models for public participation in scientific research (PPSR). X = public included in aspect; (X) = public sometimes involved in aspect

Aspects of scientific research/monitoring process:	Contractual Projects	Contributory Projects:	Collaborative Projects:	Co-Created Projects:	Collegial Projects
Choose or define question (s) for study	X			X	X
Gather information and resources	(X)			X	X
Develop explanations (hypotheses)				X	X
Design data collection methodologies			(X)	X	X
Collect samples and/or record data		X	X	X	X
Analyze samples			X	X	X
Analyze data		(X)	X	X	X
Interpret data and draw conclusions	(X)		(X)	X	X
Disseminate conclusions/translate results into action	(X)	(X)	(X)	X	X
Discuss results and ask new questions	X			X	X

Source: Shirk, J. L., H. L. Ballard, C. C. Wilderman, T. Phillips, A. Wiggins, R. Jordan, E. McCallie, M. Minarchek, B. V. Lewenstein, M. E. Krasny, and R. Bonney. 2012. Public participation in scientific research: a framework for deliberate design. *Ecology and Society* 17(2): 29. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5751/ES-04705-170229>